

DEVELOPMENT OF BONDED STRAIN GAGE TECHNIQUES FOR ELEVATED
TEMPERATURE TESTING OF WET COMPOSITES USING BISMALLEIMIDE FILM

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ABSTRACT

F655, a toughened bismaleimide resin system developed for high temperature aerospace composite applications, has been successfully used as a strain gage adhesive for water-saturated composite tests. The F655 gage adhesive survived water conditioning of the test laminates at temperatures of 65 to 100 °C, and subsequent test temperatures up to 230 °C. Good adhesion was obtained on epoxy, cyanate ester, and bismaleimide based composite laminates. The technique is shown to be particularly useful for in-plane shear modulus determination of water-saturated laminates at temperatures up to 230 °C.

KEYWORDS: Adhesive; Bismaleimide; Shear Modulus; Strain Gage; Test Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite laminates at temperatures in excess of 300 °C has challenged the materials testing community to develop new techniques to accurately measure material properties at high temperatures. One of the most difficult testing requirements is the determination of elevated temperature moduli of water-saturated laminates. Conventional extensometers may be used for many tests. In other cases, such as in-plane shear moduli, strain gages are needed to measure several strains simultaneously, or to measure strain at temperatures above the use temperature of available extensometers. However, commercial strain gage adhesives are epoxy-based, and are prone to failure when used on water saturated laminates in tests above about 120 °C.

2. BACKGROUND

Currently, there are excellent epoxy-based strain gage adhesives available for composite applications that have short term use temperatures up to 370 °C (700 °F). "Short term" is important to the test engineer, who is concerned with the survival of the gage adhesive bond only as long as it takes to obtain the strain information needed for one test. Strain gage testing is therefore normally very successful for dry laminates.

Measuring the moduli of water-saturated laminates is much more complex. Testing is done after conditioning cycles that include boiling in water, humidity cabinet exposure up to 85 °C (185 °F) and 100 % R.H., and water immersion (70 °C is typical). Exposure times to achieve saturation vary from four days to several months.

There are two ways to use strain gages for wet laminate tests. The first is bonding the gage to the saturated laminate using a room temperature curing adhesive. Cyanoacrylate "instant" adhesives such as M-Bond 200 are adequate for this purpose, and may be used successfully for test temperatures up to about 100 °C. For tests above 100 °C, we have had no success using room-temperature curing epoxy-based adhesives. Gage adhesive failure appears to result from exceeding the upper use temperature of the adhesive. Although we have not investigated this problem in detail, the curing of the gage adhesive is likely adversely affected by contact with a wet laminate surface.

The second method is application of the gage to a dry laminate prior to water conditioning. Protective coatings of polyurethane, polysulfide rubbers, wax, etc., may be applied to protect the gage outer surface from environmental conditioning, but the gage adhesive remains exposed to water diffusing through the laminate. At test temperatures above about 120 °C (250 °F), the typical gage adhesive is above its wet glass transition, and adhesive failures can occur. At temperatures above 150 °C (300 °F), we experienced many adhesive failures of epoxy gage adhesives regardless of the coating applied prior to wet conditioning.

For characterization of bismaleimide matrix composites, we wanted to determine the moduli of wet laminates at test temperatures up to 230 °C (450 °F). The problem of gage adhesive failure was solved by developing techniques using bismaleimide resin film as a strain gage adhesive. Gages were applied before water conditioning, and survivability of the adhesive bond was excellent at elevated test temperatures.

3. MATERIALS

3.1. Strain Gage Adhesive Film. The material used for strain gage adhesive was an unsupported .035 mm film of Hexcel's F655. The film was coated onto release paper for ease of handling small pieces. F655 is a controlled flow, toughened bismaleimide (BMI) resin system, typically used in structural and electrical aerospace composite applications. As a structural material,

F655 maintains high strength retention to 177 °C (350 °F) wet and 232 °C (450 °F) dry. F655 also shows excellent durability and microcrack resistance in prolonged elevated temperature environments. Even though the ability to support structural load is not necessary in strain gage adhesive applications, F655 was chosen for evaluation because of its high use temperature and ease in processing.

3.2. Test Laminates. Test laminates for the gage adhesive study were made from the following prepreg products: IM7/F655 unidirectional tape, Hitex 46-8B/F655 unidirectional tape, IM7/F3900 unidirectional tape, and IM7/561-66 unidirectional tape. F3900 is Hexcel's toughened, 177°C cure epoxy resin system. Formulation 561-66 is an experimental cyanate ester resin system, recently described in ref. 1.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

4.1. Gage Application. The surface of each composite specimen was prepared by sand blasting with a micro-sand blaster to remove surface gloss only. The gaging area was cleaned with isopropanol, and gage alignment lines were drawn on the specimen. The specimen surface was heated briefly with a heat gun, then F655 film was immediately applied to the heated surface. The release paper backing was heated for 5-10 seconds to increase the tack of the F655 film. The release paper was removed promptly, and the adhesive film was allowed to cool. The adhesive was again heated for 5-10 seconds, until it was tacky, and the strain gage was placed on the adhesive. If the gage was not aligned properly the first time, reheating the back of the specimen with the heat gun allowed easy repositioning of the gage.

The installed gage was covered with a piece of FEP film, a high temperature silicone rubber pressure pad and an aluminum shim. This assembly was clamped over the gage with a small clamp. The back of the specimen was then heated for 15-20 sec with the heat gun. After cooling, the clamp, pad and film were removed, and the gage adhesive bond line inspected for voids or irregularities. In case of an imperfect installation, the specimen could be reheated, the gage removed, and additional adhesive film applied to obtain a smoother bondline.

With FEP film, rubber pad, shim, and clamp back in place, the F655 adhesive was cured for 4 hours at 177 °C (350 °F). This cure cycle compares favorably with the 1 to 2 hour cure at 177 °C required for epoxy adhesives. Gages on specimens for wet conditioning were coated with silicone rubber sealant. This step was found to be most important for protection of copper solder pads from degradation.

4.2. Environmental Conditioning. Two different methods were used to condition composite test specimens to saturation: 34 days exposure to 65 ± 2 °C and $85 \pm 4\%$ relative humidity in an environmental chamber, and 96 hours in water held just below the boiling point ($98 - 100$ °C).

4.3. Mechanical Tests. Mechanical tests were performed on an Instron Universal Test Machine. Strain gage outputs were read with Measurements Group model 2311 signal conditioning amplifiers. Micro-Measurements WK (glass fiber reinforced epoxy-phenolic backing and encapsulation), option W, style strain gages were used for all strain measurements. Testing of wet laminates was started one to two minutes after specimens reached the test temperature.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To verify that bonding strain gages with F655 has no effect on the performance of the gage itself, one strain gage was bonded to a test specimen with F655. The specimen was held for 96 hours in a water boil bath. After this conditioning, an additional gage was bonded to the same specimen with M-Bond 200. The outputs of both gages were monitored as the specimen was stressed at room temperature. The two gages gave identical results.

5.1. Test Temperatures to 140 °C (280 °F). In-plane shear modulus measurements were taken on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates of IM7/F3900 at test temperatures of 88, 104, 121, and 138 °C, using two strain gages bonded with F655 adhesive. Prior to testing, the specimens were conditioned for 34 days at 65 °C and 85% relative humidity. No gage adhesive failures occurred during testing. The results are shown in Table 1. A typical load-strain plot from these experiments is shown in Figure 1.

Table 1. In-Plane Shear Modulus of Water-Saturated IM7/F3900 Laminates. Conditioning was 34 days at 65 °C, 85% RH.

Temp. °C	In-Plane Shear Modulus, GPa Individual Results	Avg.	% CV
88	4.36, 4.73, 4.90, 4.56, 4.56	4.63	4.4
104	3.83, 4.02, 4.27, 4.10, 3.97	4.04	4.1
121	3.65, 3.62, 3.97, 3.59, 3.37	3.64	5.9
138	3.43, 2.72, 3.39, 2.88, 2.92	3.07	10.6

5.2. Test Temperatures above 140 °C. In-plane shear modulus measurements were taken on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates of IM7/F655 at test temperatures of 150 °C and 177 °C using F655 as the strain gage adhesive. Humidity conditioning was the same as for the F3900 laminates, 34 days at 65 °C, 85% RH. Again, no gage adhesive failures occurred during testing. The strain gages could typically be read to over 1% strain, as shown in Figure 2. Table 2 shows typical values of the wet in-plane shear modulus of IM7/F655 determined by this method. In-plane shear moduli were also determined on IM7/F655 after the specimens were exposed to an "accelerated" conditioning cycle of 96 hours in a water boil bath. The F655 gage adhesive survived this

conditioning and subsequent testing at 150 and 177 °C. The results were comparable to the previous results for IM7/F655, as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. In-Plane Shear Modulus of Water-Saturated IM7/F655 Laminates.
Conditioning was 34 days at 65 °C, 85% RH.

Temp. °C	In-Plane Shear Modulus, GPa Individual Results	Avg.	% CV
150	3.86, 3.52, 3.68, 3.99	3.76	5.5
177	2.70, 2.77, 2.87, 2.64, 2.77	2.75	3.1

Table 3. In-Plane Shear Modulus of Water-Saturated IM7/F655 Laminates.
Conditioning was 96 hours in boiling water.

Temp. °C	In-Plane Shear Modulus, GPa Individual Results	Avg.	% CV
150	3.55, 3.69, 3.74	3.66	2.7
177	2.50, 2.68, 2.37	2.52	6.1

At temperatures above 177 °C, we have used the same basic gage application techniques with F655 as the gage adhesive. Our experimental work has not been as extensive as that done at the lower temperatures; however, we have successfully measured the in-plane shear modulus of saturated laminates up to 230 °C. For testing at 230 °C, we have added a 2-hour postcure at 230 °C to the cure cycle of the gage adhesive. Hitex/F655 laminates were conditioned for 96 hours in a water boil bath prior to testing. Although the wet shear modulus drops considerably above 200 °C, we were able to successfully measure it at 200 and 230 °C (see Table 4).

Table 4. In-Plane Shear Modulus of Water-Saturated Hitex/F655 Laminates.
Conditioning was 96 hours in boiling water.

Test Temperature, °C	177	204	232
Shear Modulus, GPa	2.94	1.32	.669

F655 has also been used to bond gages to 561-66 cyanate ester laminates, which are very difficult to bond with epoxy-based adhesives. After a 96 hour water boil, and testing at 177 °C, we experienced no gage adhesive failures of F655 to the cyanate ester resin.

7. CONCLUSIONS

F655 resin film has proven to be a reliable strain gage adhesive for wet composite laminate testing, in situations where the strain gage adhesive must survive environmental conditioning followed by elevated test temperatures to 230 °C. The cure cycle used for F655 was comparable to that used for commercial epoxy strain gage adhesives. Further work on saturated PMR-15 laminates is planned.

8. REFERENCES

1. F. W. Lee, et al., "High Service Temperature, Damage Tolerant Prepreg Systems based on Cyanate Chemistry", 35th Int. SAMPE Symposium, April 2-5, 1990.

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NOTICE

M-Bond 200 is a product of Measurements Group, Inc. F655 and F3900 are registered trademarks of Hexcel Corp. for structural resin systems. IM7 and Hitex 46-8B are registered trademarks of Hercules Corp., and Hitco Materials Division, respectively, for intermediate modulus carbon fiber.

Figure 1. Load-strain curves for saturated $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate of IM7/F3900. Transverse strain is shown with polarity reversed.

Figure 2. Load-strain curves for saturated $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate of IM7/F655. Transverse strain is shown with polarity reversed.

